

Research Guru

Online Journal of Multidisciplinary Subjects (ISSN : 2349-266X)

Volume-12, Issue-3, December-2018

**Editor-In-Chief
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Email: researchguru125@gmail.com
Website: www.researchguru.net

UGC Approved Journal No: 63726
Impact Factor:4.081

Research Guru: Online Journal of Multidisciplinary Subjects (Peer Reviewed)

Impact Factor: 4.081

Aggression: A Comparative Study among Hindu and Muslim College Students

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Abstract:

Present study represents a comparative account of 'aggression' among Hindu and Muslim College Students. Here we have chosen 18 to 35 years old fellows Hindu and Muslim College Students. regression measurement was carried out by using 'Scale of aggression' created by Dr. Buzz and Dr. pari. After statistical analysis of all data, we found vast different in degree of Insecurity between higher and lower class youth. We have studied Future context aggression by taking three independent variables using F-Anova test with 2x2x2 factorial design.

Key words: Aggression, Hindu and Muslim, boys and girls, arts and science college

1. What is Aggression?

'The phenomenon in which one harms other to get joy' - "The psychology of Aggression buss (1961)". Aggression, in its broadest sense, is behaviour, or a disposition, that is forceful, hostile or attacking. It may occur either in retaliation or without provocation. In narrower definitions that are used in social sciences and behavioral sciences, aggression is an intention to cause harm or an act intended to increase relative social dominance. Predatory or defensive behavior between members of different species may not be considered aggression in the same sense. Aggression can take a variety of forms and can be physical or be communicated verbally or non-verbally. Aggression differs from what is commonly called assertiveness, although the terms are often used interchangeably among laypeople, e.g. an aggressive salesperson

Research Problem

"Aggression: A Comparative Study among Hindu and Muslim College Students"

Objectives of the research / Aims / Purpose

Every research problem is with some fruitful outcome. Generally researcher exhibits his study to either compare two or more facts and this defines the aim of study. Research is not only to solve any puzzle but it is done to give the answer of any genuine problem. Thus, research is done to give the answer of social, economic, political and scientific questions which will give some fruitful outcome to the society. In this way, the aim of research is to find out the solutions of aforementioned questions by exhibiting the rational scientific and research methodology. The aim of present study is as listed follow.

The main aims of this study area:

1. To measure the degree of Aggression in Hindu and Muslim community

2. To measure the degree of Aggression in Arts and Science students
3. To measure the degree of Aggression in Boys and Girls
4. To compare the degree of Aggression in Hindu and Muslim community
5. To compare the degree of Aggression in Arts and Science students
6. To compare the degree of Aggression in Boys and Girls

Hypothesis

After defining the research problem, researcher creates the hypothesis for the outcome of research. Research presumes about the possible outcomes of research. These types of guesses are designed as 'Hypothesis'. We defined the null hypothesis for present research is as following:

Null hypothesis

There is no significant difference in the degree of aggression, insecurity and personality traits among hindu and muslim, arts and science students, girls and boys.

Hypothesis of the present research are:

HO1: 'There is no significant difference between the mean of aggression among the Hindu and Muslim community students

HO2: 'There is no significant difference between the mean of aggression among the science and arts student.

Ho3. There is no significant difference in the mean of Aggression among Boys and Girls.

HO4: Interaction of community and education stream has no significant effect on the Aggression.

HO5: Interaction of community and Gender has no significant effect on the Aggression..

HO6: Interaction of Education and Gender has no significant effect on the Aggression.

HO7: Interaction of Community, Education stream and Gender has no significant effect on the Aggression

Variables

Variables have very great importance in the psychological research. As it name suggested Variables means the moiety whose value keep changing. In psychology, variables are the characteristic, virtue or any other mental measurement. According to the views of D. Ameto, variables are the moiety of animal, situation and other thing which can be measured.

In research, three main variables are always well defined. A-Dependent variables B-Independent variables and C-Controlled variables. In present study, followings are the major variables.

A. Independent Variables

- | | |
|-----------------------|--------------------------|
| I. Community: | Hindu and Muslim |
| II. Education: | Arts and Science stream. |
| III. Gender: | Boys and Girls |

B. Dependent Variables

- I. Aggression

C. Control Variables

- I. Equal numbers of gender
- II. Same time for all experiments (Teat time)
- III. Same test will be given to all students
- IV. Same method will be used for data analysis
- V. Age limit taken: 18-25 years
- VI. Only undergraduate (UG) students will be taken in account

Sample

'Probability sampling is the only approach that malkes possible representative sampling plan'- **Isisor Chein'**

Sample is the part of population. The aim of sampling is to get an idea about particular characteristics of whole population by analyzing the small part of population- the sample. In present study, sampling is done from various arts and science college affiliated to Sardar Patel University.

Arts colleges from where sampling was done

1. Nalini, arvind and T.V. Patel arts college Vallbh Vidyanagar (Sardar Patel University)
2. Anand arts college, Anand (Sardar Patel University)
3. N. S. Patel Arts college, Anand. (Sardar Patel University)
4. Bhikhabhai Arts college, Anand (Sardar Patel University)

Sciences colleges from where sampling was done

1. V. P. and R.P.T.P. science college, Vallabh Vidyanagar (Sardar Patel University)
2. N. V. Patel Science College Vallabh Vidyanagar (Sardar Patel University)
3. M. B. Patel science college, Anand (Sardar Patel University)
4. P. M. Patel science college, Anand (Sardar Patel University)

Sample is selected from the aforementioned colleges if Sardar Patel University. We have visited the colleges after taking the permission from principal or any other higher authority. We have also collected the information regarding the total number of students, their subjects and their class distribution. We have made student to fill the provided questionnaire containing various measure.

As per factorial design we will select total 320 youngsters, out of which 160 from Hindu and 160 from Muslim. These 160 will be further divided in 80-80; 80 from Arts stream and 80 from science stream. These 80 will be further divided in 40-40; 40 are girls and 40 are Boys.

Table.1 Sample selection procedure of the subjects as per the given

<i>Hindu</i>	<i>Arts</i>	<i>Boys</i>	<i>40</i>	<i>80</i>	<i>160</i>	<i>320</i>
		<i>Girls</i>	<i>40</i>			
	<i>Science</i>	<i>Boys</i>	<i>40</i>	<i>80</i>		
		<i>Girls</i>	<i>40</i>			
<i>Muslim</i>	<i>Arts</i>	<i>Boys</i>	<i>40</i>	<i>80</i>	<i>160</i>	
		<i>Girls</i>	<i>40</i>			
	<i>Science</i>	<i>Boys</i>	<i>40</i>	<i>80</i>		
		<i>Girls</i>	<i>40</i>			

Tools

Researchers take various useful tools to measure psychological functions. The right tool is selected to validate the created hypothesis. Sometime researchers use more than one tools for solving/measuring complex phenomenon, ultimately give very accurate results. In present study, following listed tools are used to measure different psychological moiety.

Personal information sheet

In present study, we have prepared Personal information sheet on the basis of independent variables. In which the name, educational qualification, community, religion, age etc are included.

Collection of Data

Data was collected by using the tools of Dr. Buzz and peri, Dr. Beena Shah and Dr. R.B. cattle for the aggression, insecurity and personality traits, respectively.

Data collected during July, august, September and October 2014 from the sample of arts and sciences colleges' girls and boys. Sample size was 320 students.

We have gone to colleges with prior permission of higher authorities. Student were pre-informed that the given information sheet is only for study purpose. They were also guided at the place where they feel difficulties in filling form.

Research design

“Research design is the plan, structure of investigations, conceived so as to research questions”

Research design is the answer of the questions of investigation. So research design is the most important in the research methodology. In this research we want to find out the comparative account of Aggression, Insecurity and Personality trait of Hindu and Muslim girls and Boys.

For that we will use the factor analysis statistical method and $2 \times 2 \times 2$ Factorial design will be applied for the data collection and data analysis purpose.

Table .2 showing the information regarding the sample and information sheets

Source	A1		A2		Total
	B1	B2	B1	B2	
C1	40	40	40	40	160
C2	40	40	40	40	160
Total sample	80	80	80	80	320

Clarification of above classification

- A. Community
 - A1- Hindu community
 - A2- Muslim community
- B. Education
 - B1-Arts faculty
 - B2- Science faculty
- C. Gender
 - C1- Girls
 - C2- Boys

Statistical analysis

The collected data were analyzed by 2×2×2 Factorial. F-test ANOVA was used for statistical analysis of data. The difference in mean is counted for each independent factor. The value of mean and their graphs were taken in account to analyze raw data.

Analysis and inferences

Community, Education stream and Gender context aggression

Community, Education stream and Gender context aggression was investigated through independent and inter-dependent variables on the basis of the constructed null hypothesis (1 to 7). To do so, we have used ANOVA in the frame of (2×2×2). On the basis of which, we calculated the ‘F’ – values for the aggression of eight different groups. Their Mead and standard deviations (SD) are shown in Table.

Table 3: Mean and their S.D. for community, education stream and gender context aggression

Community	Stream	Statistics	Gender	
			Boys	Girls
Hindu	Arts	Mean(M)	75.90	81.97
		(S.D)	16.41	9.45
		Number (N)	40	40
	Science	Mean(M)	74.75	79.00
		(S.D)	12.09	7.48
		Number (N)	40	40
Muslim	Arts	Mean(M)	83.72	90.15
		(S.D)	7.67	13.65
		Number (N)	40	40
	Science	Mean(M)	69.87	100.40
		(S.D)	7.73	12.61
		Number (N)	40	40

Table 4: Difference between mean of community, education stream and gender context aggression

Independent Variable	Number	Mean	Defrents
Hindu (A1)	160	75.38	10,65
Muslim (A2)	160	86.03	
Arts (B1)	160	82.93	2.67
Science (B2)	160	80.26	
Boys (C1)	160	76.06	11.07
Girls (C2)	160	87.13	

Table 5: Summery of ANOVA (2×2×2) analysis of community, education stream and gender context aggression (Level of Significant 0.05 < 3.87 and 0.01 < 6.72)

Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Sum of Squares	F Value	Level of Sig
Community (A)	6301.250	1	6301.250	53.35	0.01
Stream (b)	572.450	1	572.450	4.84	0.05

Gender (C)	9812.450	1	9812.450	83.08	0.01
AxB	61.250	1	61.250	.519	N.S
AxC	4380.800	1	4380.800	37.09	0.01
BxC	1862.450	1	1862.450	15.77	0.01
AxBxC	4176.050	1	4176.050	35.36	0.01
Error	36848.100	312	118.103		
Total	2194754.000	320			
T.S.S.	64014.800	319			

Type of community and Aggression

To know that, is there any difference in mean of Aggression between the Hindu and Muslim community, the null hypothesis (HO01) was constructed previously.

HO1: 'There is no significant difference between the mean of aggression among the Hindu and Muslim community students

Table 4.2 indicated that the means of aggression of hindu and muslim community student are 75.38 and 86.03. The difference between means is 10.65. This is very high. It also shows that the F- value of between type of community and aggression is 53.35 (Table 4.3). This value is significant with the p-value 0.01. Here, on the basis of the obtained results, the null hypothesis (HO1) is rejected and there is the significant difference is observed between the aggression between the muslim and hindu community student. The results are depicted in Graph 4.1 (A1-A2).

Education stream and Aggression

To know that, is there any difference in mean of Aggression between the science and arts student, the null hypothesis (HO02) was constructed previously.

HO2: 'There is no significant difference between the mean of aggression among the science and arts student

Table 4.2 indicated that the means of aggression of the science and arts student are 82.93 and 80.25. The difference between mean is 2.67. It also shows that the F- value of between type of community and aggression is 4.84 (Table 4.3). This value is significant with the p-value 0.05. Here, on the basis of the obtained results, the null hypothesis (HO2) is rejected and there is the significant difference is observed between the aggression between the science and arts student. The results are depicted in Graph 4.1 (B1-B2).

Gender and Aggression

To know that, is there any difference in mean of Aggression between the girls and boys student, the null hypothesis (HO03) was constructed previously.

HO3: 'There is no significant difference between the mean of aggression among the girls and boys student

Table 4.2 indicated that the means of aggression of the girls and boys student are 76.06 and 87.13. The difference between mean is 11.07. It also shows that the F- value of between type of community and aggression is 82.08 (Table 4.3). This value is significant with the p-value 0.01. Here, on the basis of the obtained results, the null hypothesis (HO3) is rejected and there is the significant difference is observed between the aggression between the girls and boys student. The results are depicted in Graph 4.1 (C1-C2).

Effect of Interaction between Community and Education stream on Aggression (AxB)

To know that, is there any effect of interaction of community and education stream on the mean of Aggression, the null hypothesis (HO4) was constructed previously.

HO4: Interaction of community and education stream has no significant effect on the Aggression.

Table 4.3 indicated that the F- value for the interaction of community and education stream on the mean of Aggression is 0.519. Here, on the basis of the obtained results, the null hypothesis (HO4) is accepted and there is no the significant effect of interaction of community and education stream on the aggression.

Effect of Interaction between Community and Gender on Aggression (AxC)

To know that, is there any effect of interaction of community and Gender on the mean of Aggression, the null hypothesis (HO5) was constructed previously.

HO5: Interaction of community and Gender has no significant effect on the Aggression.

Table 4.3 indicated that the F- value for the interaction of community and Gender on the mean of Aggression is 37.09. This value is significant with the p-value 0.01. Here, on the basis of the obtained results, the null hypothesis (HO5) is rejected and there is significant effect of interaction of community and gender on the aggression.

Effect of Interaction between Education and Gender on Aggression (BxC)

To know that, is there any effect of interaction of Education and Gender on the mean of Aggression, the null hypothesis (HO6) was constructed previously.

HO6: Interaction of Education and Gender has no significant effect on the Aggression.

Table 4.3 indicated that the F- value for the interaction of Education and Gender on the mean of Aggression is 15.77. This value is significant with the p-value 0.01. Here, on the basis of the obtained results, the null hypothesis (HO6) is rejected and there is significant effect of interaction of Education and Gender on the aggression.

Effect of Interaction between Community, Education stream and Gender on Aggression (AxBxC)

To know that, is there any effect of interaction of Community, Education stream and Gender on the mean of Aggression, the null hypothesis (HO7) was constructed previously.

HO7: Interaction of Community, Education stream and Gender has no significant effect on the Aggression.

Table 4.3 indicated that the F- value for the interaction of Community, Education stream and Gender on the mean of Aggression is 35.36. This value is significant with the p-value 0.01. Here, on the basis of the obtained results, the null hypothesis (HO7) is rejected and there the significant effect of interaction of Community, Education stream and Gender on the aggression.

❖ Results

1. There is the significant difference observed between the mean of aggression among the Hindu and Muslim community students.

2. There is the significant difference observed between the mean of aggression among the Arts and science students.
3. There is the significant difference observed between the mean of aggression among the Boys and Girls community students.
4. Interaction of community and education stream has no significant effect on the Aggression.
5. Interaction of community and Gender has the significant effect on the Aggression.
6. Interaction of Education and Gender has the significant effect on the Aggression.
7. Interaction of Community, Education stream and Gender has the significant effect on the Aggression.

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